

A comparative study on viscosities of some hydrated and anhydrous salts of transition metal sulphates and magnesium sulphate in water at different temperatures

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Abstract : Relative viscosities for the aqueous solutions of some hydrated and anhydrous salts of transition metal sulphates viz. cobalt sulphate, nickel sulphate, copper sulphate and zinc sulphate, and magnesium sulphate have been determined (in the concentration range $0.005\text{--}0.100 \pm 0.001 \text{ mol kg}^{-1}$) at five equidistant [298.15, 303.15, 308.15, 313.15 and 318.15 K] temperatures. The data have been evaluated using Jones-Dole equation and the obtained parameters have been interpreted in terms of ion-ion and ion-solvent interactions. The hydrated salts of transition metal sulphates and magnesium sulphate act as structure-makers/promoters while the anhydrous salts act as structure-breakers in water i.e. just the removal of water of crystallization changes the behaviour of salts all together.

Keywords : Viscosity, hydrated and anhydrous salts, water.

Introduction

Comparative behaviour of hydrated and anhydrous salts of transition metal sulphates and magnesium sulphate in water are expected to highlight the role of water of crystallization in influencing the viscosity B -coefficients. Hence, the present study has been undertaken to provide better understanding of the comparative nature of hydrated and anhydrous salts of transition metal sulphates and magnesium sulphate in water.

Results and discussion

The relative viscosities and densities for the aqueous solutions of hydrated and anhydrous salts of transition metal sulphates viz. cobalt sulphate, nickel sulphate, copper sulphate and zinc sulphate, and magnesium sulphate were determined at different temperatures [298.15, 303.15, 308.15, 313.15 and 318.15 K]. The experimental results of the relative viscosities of the hydrated and anhydrous salts have been analysed by Jones-Dole equation

$$\eta_r = \eta/\eta_0 = 1 + A\sqrt{c} + Bc$$

or

$$(\eta_r - 1)/\sqrt{c} = A + B\sqrt{c} \quad (1)$$

where η and η_0 are the viscosities of solution and solvent (water), respectively, and c is molar concentration. A and B are the constants characteristic of ion-ion and ion-solvent interactions, respectively.

The plots of $(\eta_r - 1)/\sqrt{c}$ versus \sqrt{c} , for all the hydrated and anhydrous salts of transition metal sulphates and magnesium sulphate, were found to be linear, with least scatter in water at different temperatures. The values of A and B parameters have been calculated using the least-square method by fitting the experimental results in Jones-Dole equation and these values along with standard errors, obtained in water at different temperatures are recorded in Table 1. The values of parameter- A are positive for the aqueous solutions of all the hydrated salts of transition metal sulphates and magnesium sulphate at all

Table 1. Values of A ($\text{dm}^{3/2} \text{ mol}^{-1/2}$) and B ($\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) of Jones-Dole equation for hydrated and anhydrous salts of transition metal sulphates and magnesium sulphate in water at different temperatures (error < 1%)

Parameter	Temp. (K)				
	298.15	303.15	308.15	313.15	318.15
CoSO ₄ .7H ₂ O (A)	10.49	12.43	14.65	17.06	18.80
(B)	0.304	0.303	0.301	0.279	0.261
NiSO ₄ .6H ₂ O (A)	10.85	12.31	13.51	14.63	15.60
(B)	0.219	0.213	0.211	0.208	0.206
CuSO ₄ .5H ₂ O (A)	10.19	12.12	14.22	16.14	18.04
(B)	0.345	0.330	0.313	0.307	0.298
ZnSO ₄ .7H ₂ O (A)	10.22	12.22	14.12	16.06	17.93
(B)	0.342	0.333	0.320	0.309	0.297
MgSO ₄ .7H ₂ O (A)	8.28	10.16	12.14	13.95	15.21
(B)	0.362	0.358	0.348	0.337	0.327

Table-1 (contd.)

CoSO ₄	(A)	9.61	7.67	4.84	3.04	0.68
	(B)	0.292	0.314	0.355	0.369	0.396
NiSO ₄	(A)	8.03	6.45	4.40	2.72	0.764
	(B)	0.318	0.333	0.343	0.355	0.364
CuSO ₄	(A)	9.41	7.38	5.28	2.75	0.79
	(B)	0.303	0.329	0.338	0.356	0.371
ZnSO ₄	(A)	8.59	6.96	4.60	3.10	1.05
	(B)	0.339	0.352	0.368	0.380	0.393
MgSO ₄	(A)	7.96	6.66	4.43	2.92	0.84
	(B)	0.283	0.289	0.308	0.317	0.337

temperatures and increase with the increase of temperature, for an individual hydrated salt, showing that ion-ion interactions are strengthened with the rise in temperature. A perusal of Table 1 also shows that the values of *A*-parameter are positive and decrease with the rise in temperature, for an individual anhydrous salt, showing that ion-ion interactions are weakened with the increase of temperature.

The *B*-coefficients for the aqueous solutions of hydrated salts of transition metal sulphates and magnesium sulphate are positive at all temperatures and the value of *B*-coefficient, for an individual hydrated salt in water, decreases with temperature, showing that ion-solvent interactions are weakened with the rise in temperature. The negative temperature coefficient (i.e. dB/dT), for the aqueous solutions of all the hydrated salts of transition metal sulphates and magnesium sulphate, suggests that these salts act as structure-makers/promoters in water.

The values of *B*-coefficients for all the anhydrous salts of transition metal sulphates and magnesium sulphate in water, are positive at all temperatures and increase with the temperature, suggesting that ion-solvent interactions are strengthened with the increase in temperature. The positive temperature coefficient (i.e. dB/dT), for the anhydrous salts of transition metal sulphates and magnesium sulphate in water, suggests that these anhydrous salts act as structure breakers in water.

If the viscosity results of hydrated and anhydrous salts of transition metal sulphates and magnesium sulphate in water are compared, it can be concluded that the behaviour of the hydrated salts changes from structure-makers to structure-breakers simply on the removal of water of crystallization.

Experimental

The hydrated sulphates of cobalt [CoSO₄·7H₂O], nickel [NiSO₄·6H₂O], copper [CuSO₄·5H₂O], zinc [ZnSO₄·7H₂O] and magnesium [MgSO₄·7H₂O] (A.R.) were used for present study. The water of crystallization in all the hydrated and anhydrous salts was estimated by the standard method¹. The anhydrous salts were prepared after repeated heating and cooling in a desiccator, until constant weight of the salt was obtained¹. After complete dehydration, these salts were always placed over P₂O₅ in a desiccator to keep them in dry atmosphere. Freshly distilled conductivity water (sp. cond. $\sim 10^{-6} \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) was used for preparing aqueous solutions and as standard liquid.

All the aqueous solutions of hydrated and anhydrous salts of transition metal sulphates and magnesium sulphate were made by weight and molalities, *m*, were converted into molarities, *c*, using the standard expression², $c = 1000 \text{ dm} / (1000 + mM_2)$, where *d* is the solution density and *M*₂ molecular weight of an hydrated or anhydrous salt.

For density measurements, an apparatus similar to the one reported by Ward and Millero and described elsewhere was used³. The accuracy in density measurement was of $\pm 1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ g cm}^{-3}$. The relative viscosities were measured at the desired temperature using Ostwald's suspended level type viscometer with a flow time of 375 s for water at 298.15 K. Runs were repeated until three successive determinations were obtained within ± 0.1 s. Since all the flow times were greater than 100 s, kinetic energy correction was not necessary. The relative viscosities of the solutions (η_r) were calculated by the usual procedure⁴. Density and viscosity measurements were carried out in a well-stirred water-bath whose temperature was controlled to ± 0.01 K.

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